

ACCESS COMMUNITY WORKSHOP REPORT

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Acknowledgement of Country

We at ACCESS-NRI acknowledge the Traditional Owners of the land on which our research infrastructure and community operate across Australia and pay our respects to Elders past and present. We recognise the thousands of years of accumulated knowledge and deep connection they have with all the Earth systems we simulate.

2023 ACCESS Community Workshop

The 2023 ACCESS Community Workshop was held over 5-6 September 2023 online and in Canberra, ACT on Ngunnawal and Ngambri country. The workshop was held to:

- Bring together people across the ACCESS community to present and discuss current and emerging topics (both technical and scientific)
- Provide updates on ACCESS-NRI activities and plan
- Support the community Working Groups and foster new and existing community-wide collaborations
- Provide a forum for community feedback on ACCESS-NRI activities and priorities
- Deliver training on ACCESS-related software, data, and tools

ACCESS-NRI also hosted several related pre- and post-workshop events. The week kicked off with ACCESS-NRI's first user training day (4 September) and concluded with 6 Community Working Group workshops held over 7-8 September.

Participants

We had 190 registrations for the workshop (120 in person, 70 virtual) from:

- Australian universities: University of New South Wales, University of Tasmania, Monash University, Australian National University, University of Melbourne, Murdoch University, University of Southern Queensland, University of Adelaide.
- National scientific organisations: CSIRO, Bureau of Meteorology, National Environmental Science Program (NESP), ARC Centre of Excellence for Climate Extremes (CLEX), and the Australian Antarctic Division (AAD).
- Government representatives: the Department of Education, Department of Climate Change, Energy, the Environment and Water (DCCEEW), Climate Change Authority, NSW Department of Primary Industries, and NSW Department of Planning and Environment.
- International universities and scientific institutions: Met Office (UK), NOAA Geophysical Fluid Dynamics Laboratory and Princeton University (USA), UCAR (USA), Victoria University of Wellington (NZ), and University of Canterbury (NZ).
- Research infrastructures: ACCESS-NRI, NCI, and TERN and AARNet.
- Other: Deloitte, Universiti Teknologi Petronas (Malaysia), University of Hyderabad (India) and Guntonia Investments.

The pre- and post-workshop events included 59 registered attendees for the training day and 222 (141 in-person, 81 virtual) for the Community Working Group workshops. More details on the participants can be found in the Appendix 1.

The topics were selected to bring together people with shared interests across the diverse community. The discussion included sharing the status of current work, capturing future ACCESS community needs and identifying areas in need of support. Detailed summaries of the individual discussion groups can be found in the Appendix 2.

The workshop closed with the presentation of the best poster awards, which attendees voted on through the [online poster gallery](#). They winners included:

- **Best Student Poster:** Zijin Chen (IMAS/AAPP) for “[How sea ice affects the Southern Ocean water masses: An ACCESS case study](#)”
- **1st place:** Yu Wang (AAPP/IMAS/UTAS) for “[Modelling Ice Sheet Changes in the Wilkes Subglacial Basin before 2500: How Sensitive Are Our Predictions?](#)”
- **2nd place:** Abhik Santra (Monash) for “[Multiweek prediction & Attribution of the Black Saturday heatwave event in south-eastern Australia](#)”
- **3rd place:** Kial Stewart (ANU) for “[The Climate & Fluid Physics Laboratory](#)”

Outcomes

A major focus of the 2023 workshop was continued community building and support for the community Working Groups (WGs). The opening invited science talks from each WG helped showcase ACCESS science across the community. After a busy year of recruitment and establishment, the workshop also provided an opportunity for ACCESS-NRI to present highlights of work ramping up across the teams and to receive community feedback. In addition to the Director’s update, ACCESS-NRI had 17 presentations (2 talks, 6 lightning and 9 posters).

Breakout sessions included constructive discussion on cross-cutting community topics. In the case of the *Next ACCESS models* breakout group, the timing of the workshop allowed the community to provide feedback on the proposed development pathways for an ACCESS CMIP7 submission. For many of the other groups, the breakouts raised awareness of shared areas of interest, current work occurring across the community and areas for future collaboration. The breakout discussions also captured current and future science and infrastructure requirements, including where ACCESS-NRI can provide support.

Priority areas included:

- **CMIP7**
 - Model development for ACCESS contribution to CMIP7
 - CMIP7 champion in each of the ACCESS-NRI working groups

- ESMValTool support
 - Webinar training
 - Integration of new agreed-upon metrics to support CMIP7 model development
- **Model development**
 - Potential for a set of idealised experiments
 - Ability to customise regional and/or nested models
 - Improving software tools for ancillary files and working with restart files
 - Coupling of ice sheets into ACCESS
- **Model evaluation and data management**
 - Develop an evaluation framework for regional models
 - Curate, store, and manage reference datasets to support released experiments, model evaluation and machine learning (e.g., observations, reanalyses)
 - Data wrangling and post-processing tools - including output sharing

The workshop received very positive feedback with 99% of survey responses¹ finding this year's workshop valuable and 95% reporting that the workshop aims were met. The most valuable aspects reported included bringing people together and learning about the latest developments across the diverse community. Collaboration, networking and the range of science and technical talks, including the international keynote speakers, were also commonly noted favourably in the responses. We also received many helpful suggestions that will help improve future workshops, including the online/hybrid experience, venue requirements, program timing and the balance of session types. Planning for the 2024 workshop is already underway and the ACCESS-NRI team looks forward to working with the community and incorporating this feedback into next year's event.

Acknowledgements

Thank you to our partners, ACCESS-NRI team and members of the ACCESS community for their contributions throughout the workshop and related events. We also thank the Program Committee (Natalia Bateman, Claire Carouge, Edward Doddridge, Kelsey Druken, Nathan Eizenberg, Ben Evans, Ian Harman, Yi Huang, Debbie Hudson, Wilma Huneke, David Hutchinson, Andrew Kiss, Felicity McCormack, Adele Morrison, Kim Reid, Paul Spence, Anna Ukkola, Matthew Woodhouse) for their valuable contributions, time and help making this a successful workshop. Finally thanks to Harshula Jayasuriya and Davide Marchegiani for the photography and videography during the workshop.

¹ Workshop survey received 68 responses.

APPENDIX 1: Workshop Attendees

Participant organisations

Figure 1. Reported organisations of the registered participants.

Participant Roles

Figure 2. Report roles of the registered participants.

Career stages

Figure 3. Reported career stages of the registered participants.

(a) Experience with ACCESS models, components or configurations

(b) Experience with ACCESS data

Figure 4. (a) Reported experience with ACCESS models, components, or configurations from registered participants. (b) Reported experience with ACCESS related data (model outputs or inputs).

APPENDIX 2: Breakout Summaries

The following pages include summaries of the breakout discussions in Sessions 7 and 8.

Topic 1: Next ACCESS models (including CMIP7)

Breakout aim: Provide feedback on the proposed development pathways and grow the community effort on the CMIP7 submission.

Summary:

- **Two main things to consider:**
 1. Model fit for purpose
 2. Which MIPs should we commit to?
- Can't do everything – community needs, wishes, balance
 - If we plan for ESM3, we get CM3 for free
 - CM3 is an intermediate step for getting to ESM3
 - Maybe high res MIP leverages off CM3 and branches off there
- Need to be able to tune, parametrise properly during the process – need to build this into the timeline and the end applications / resolutions
- Timeline – don't have scale of resources needed
- Need models developed now so can start testing in ~5 months
- UM coupling with NUOPC ok
- CABLE has new science – problematic with timeline
- GFDL experiences – get coupled model tuned first then add in BGC
- Cable coupling into UM is technically complicated and the science of CABLE really needs to be carefully considered
- CABLE3 should be able to be coupled into UM, CABLE4 more of a problem
- Will CABLE3 be ok if we can't get to CABLE4? No – not if we want to simulate the carbon cycle. Prioritising CABLE4 is essential if we want to run emissions driven simulations.
- How do we put this together?
- Other things could be done, and CABLE4 added in slightly later. Resourcing (people) of CABLE4 is a challenge
- CMIP5 and CMIP6 both had an ambitious model and a fallback model – it does split resources but do need consider – previous generation CMIP models submitted to new CMIP do tend to be well taken up in literature
- Don't want to risk not having a model for CMIP fast track timescale

- CABLE3 needed for CABLE4 – CABLE3 needs testing too, could be done in ESM1.5 – not even clear with UM version will be used – GAL climate sensitivity not suitable as is
- CABLE4 biggest risk to getting model up – we know the path, but we don't know how to do it – CABLE4 essential but maybe not deliverable
- CABLE4 work, after getting CABLE3 in, is 18 months – timeline way out
- Other model components – NUOPC, ocean/sea ice
- Ocean BGC could be improved
- MIPs – ISMIP6 was out of cycle (used CMIP5 output), hope is that it will come into alignment, i.e. ISMIP7 uses CMIP7 output – consideration that output from CMIP7 timeline will feed into other MIPs
- Won't have a coupled ice sheet so need ISMIP7 activity
- Coupling OM3 and UM together will still bring unknowns – need some form of OM3 to start coupling, even if not final version – iterative process
- What kind of model throughput / speed are we aiming for – will affect what types of simulations that we can contribute to (e.g. low speeds will prohibit paleo runs)
- Prioritising MIPs – a vast number that we want to do – need compute time, data storage, ability to process – no funding for compute/space at NRI
- In previous CMIPs, compute time and storage provided by CSIRO – not a small cost

Topic 2: ACCESS Model Evaluation - forecasting/high-resolution modelling focus

Breakout aim: What are the current and future needs and where could ACCESS-NRI and NCI help support?

Summary:

- **What's the current status?**
 - Regional MOM6 workflow
 - MetOffice tools for pre-processing, validation statistics, open to allow community contribution
 - COSIMA cookbooks with examples of validation/comparison workflow
- **What tools, workflows and data are needed now?**
 - Observations (e.g., station data) not necessarily open and easily finable/available
 - Process based evaluation to complement statistical evaluation (flexibility)
 - What satellite data is needed by the community? For which periods?
 - Ability to store/analyse large quantities of data
 - Cultivated examples showing effective ways to use e.g., Dask
 - Effective use of Scratch store
 - Examples of how to tinker with models e.g., following David Hutchinson's talk.
 - Need some more visibility and findability on existing tools, e.g., with the UM
- **What new capabilities will be needed in a few years time?**
 - Ongoing training
 - Ocean/Atmosphere coupling
 - LFRIC upcoming.
 - Met Office developing a high res. model evaluation tools
 - Met+ toolkit for model availability
 - Ability to generate high quality visualisations
 - Observing platform (e.g., satellite/Argo) emulators. SWOT simulator and Argo Virtual fleet and could provide an example: https://github.com/CNES/swot_simulator, https://github.com/euroargodev/VirtualFleet_GulfStream
 - Cloud based workflows
- **What can ACCESS-NRI and NCI do to support?**
 - Follow up with Bureau regarding datasets
 - Chris C. & Ryan to share examples of workflows for rechunking/zarrifying etc...
 - Potential for a set of cultivated idealised/tinkered experiments.
 - Example workflows for UM/MOM6/ACCESS of how to modify the topography, land-sea mask, land use
 - Talk to the Bureau about Met+ availability/training

- Cultivated list of cloud based datasets/examples (eg. https://github.com/pangeo-data/pangeo-era5/blob/master/lazy_loading_expts.ipynb)
- Confusion around data storage, curation and stewardship. Data and curation and steward literacy training? Examples from the AUS2200 to demonstrate reproducibility/replicability.

Topic 3: Machine learning and new techniques

Breakout aim: What are the current and future needs and where could ACCESS-NRI and NCI help support?

Summary:

- Most of the attendees were merely curious about ML, relatively few doing anything...yet
- Current or planned uses include:
 - downscaling e.g. to agricultural impacts, coastal wave heights
 - empirical ML prediction (speed, accuracy)
 - physics emulators / hybrid models (speed, accuracy)
 - learn factors leading to drought (understanding)
- NCI is substantially supporting ML: houses a few predictive models such as PanguWeather and FourCastNet, as well as supporting a toolset
- Some resources identified: ECMWF MOOC, CCAI, review paper
- Discussed some aspects of how ML works: how to use, challenges such as generalisability
- Main problem is lack of time / dedicated human power especially AI/ML experts.
- Important needs around data curation and dataset completeness for ML value
- Important role for this group to bring people together
 - Forecast and Prediction Working Group, meeting tomorrow
 - Support for a larger meeting that includes ML as well as climate people
- NRI could help with
 - data curation
 - support for R
 - help in finding information
 - coordinate support through the Hive forum
- We can help NRI by Gadi users updating their project descriptions—currently don't know how many resources ML is using

Topic 4: ACCESS Model Evaluation - climate models focus

Breakout aim: What are the current and future needs and where could ACCESS-NRI and NCI help support?

Summary:

- **What's the current status across the community?**
 - A lot of experience exists across the community. What's needed is a way to bring together that experience into a single evaluation framework. ESMValTool provides just that.
 - Lot's already done for the Australian Climate Service that could potentially be leveraged
- **What tools, workflows and data are needed now?**
 - ESMValTool may be run as part of CMIP submission process. Having that tool available to run ourselves is important. It is made available through the ACCESS-NRI (including major recipes from CMIP5/6) but need to get people using it and provide training.
 - ACCESS-NRI plan is to join EMSValTool Consortium and push ESMValTool in Australia as part of model evaluation.
 - Need to understand what it is we want to look at/evaluate. The tools are one thing, but what do we actually want to look at with these tools? Need to formulate this list. That also provides a feedback mechanism for model development. ACCESS-NRI working groups important for this.
 - Aspirations to include clivar metrics in ESMValTool. These could be very important for ENSO evaluation/development and more. Also, many other ocean diagnostics (AMOC, IOD, SAM etc). Different communities each have specific metrics/diagnostics that need to be looked at.
 - ESM: main focus on carbon cycle. Need standard evaluation workflows for those.
 - Is there a need for something like a hackathon on CMIP model evaluation? Bring together different interested folks to share, develop, agree upon metrics/diagnostics and develop a single implementation. This was a popular idea.
 - Split work into a) stuff that has to be done, b) stuff that is less urgent.
 - Need for runtime metrics/diagnostics to check in on models as they run. Being developed at the ACCESS-NRI.
 - Need to evaluate existing metrics in ESMValTool etc to work out which are most important/relevant to us.
 - One ensemble member is often not sufficient to properly evaluate a model - multiple members are needed.
 - Reference dataset ("observations") are also very important. There is no single source of truth for most (all?) metrics/diagnostics. Need to agree on/prioritise datasets.
 - Do we need to be careful putting things on the Hive during the model evaluation stages (or generally) that could be exploited by bad actors?

- **What new capabilities will be needed in a few years time?**
 - Work plan (before Q1 2024):
 - Work out what metrics/diagnostics we want (who coordinates? ACCESS-NRI through working groups? Kick things off with a hackathon?)
 - Leverage what already exists (e.g. already in ESMValTool)
 - Get new scientists / students involved
 - Add what doesn't exist (e.g. wrap/translate as ESMValTool recipes with ACCESS-NRI support)
 - Prioritise metrics/diagnostics
- **What can ACCESS-NRI and NCI do to support?**
 - CMIP7 champion in each of the ACCESS-NRI working groups - to connect for evaluation etc.
 - Webinar training introducing ESMValTool - including what's already there
 - Support for integrating agreed-upon metrics into ESMValTool (that aren't already there)
 - Store/manage reference datasets (e.g. observations, reanalyses)

Topic 5: High-resolution modelling (including regional/coastal modelling)

Breakout aim: What are the current and future needs and where could ACCESS-NRI help support?

Summary:

- **What's the current status?**
 - Atm-Land:
 - Define hi-res as km-scale regionally and 10 km for global NWP and 25 km for climate globally
 - Bureau forecasts are at or approach these scales, urban work at Unis
 - CCAM/BARPA/WRF for downscaling and science
 - Aus2200
 - Ocean:
 - Regional MOM6-SIS2 configs (tools available to easily setup new configs, EAC 1/10 and 1/30th and ensembles and tides, Panantarctic, ERA5 forced global 1/4deg. Suggestion from Bob to share these with the fortnightly MOM6 regional.
 - Coastal (NRI has applied for funding to include this community). Some use ROMS, CSIRO is moving to MPAS.
 - Coupled:
 - ACCESS CM at N96 atmosphere/0.25 deg Ocean (MOM5); ACCESS-S2 N216 (0.8deg lat, 0.5deg lon) Atmosphere/ 0.25 deg Ocean (NEMO)
 - CROCO / WRF, 1/4deg atmos, 1/12 ocean
 - Elmer/ROMS regional coupled model
 - MITgcm/WRF Ross Sea, 10km
- **What are the current plans and ambitions?**
 - Atmos/Land:
 - Collaborations and plans for km-scale global are emerging (Bureau and W21C)
 - Regional: sub km scale (Bureau, urban work at Unis - CLEX)
 - Ice:
 - Elmer ISMIP
 - Ocean:
 - COSIMA - 1/25th deg global OM3 with WW3
 - Coupled:
 - Global: 25km both Atm/Land and Ocean/Sea-Ice by 2026 in W21C, 10 km in all spheres by 2028
 - Bureau Forecasts coupled by 2025/2026 - 12 km
 - 0.1deg ocean, N96 atmos/land
 - Regional:
 - 1.5km atm/land/ocean to be developed for regional forecasting at the Bureau

- W21C: Large-domain (Indo-Pacific) coupled model for science at km-scale (consider merger with the pan-Antarctica domain)
 - Bureau: DA at 1.5 km
- **What is the new science we want to be able to do in the next few years?**
 - ATM-Land:
 - Urban
 - Coasts, inundation, and mountains and their effects weather, climate and impacts
 - Lateral flows of water on the land surface
 - Improved land surface to better link to observations (DA, ML, ...) - Interactive vegetation
 - Fires
 - Better understanding and representation of convection/rainfall process
 - How do we best do scale interactions? - refined grids, two-way nesting, global
 - Weather systems and how they change in the future
 - Large domain modelling at high resolution
 - Ensembles
 - Stratospheric circulations
 - High-latitude processes
 - Ocean:
 - Impact of small-scale features on climate / large-scale circulation
 - Higher resolution - (energising eddies)
 - Land-ice interaction, ice shelf cavities
 - Coupled:
 - The role of small-scale coupling on weather and climate phenomena and their changes with climate change
 - Impacts studies over continents
 - Routing and streamflows - better water cycles and budgets
 - Multi-hazard compound event prediction
 - Process studies across all spheres
- **What can ACCESS-NRI do to support?**
 - Atm-Land
 - Support for high-resolution versions if the AL model both regional and global
 - Input data sets
 - Evaluation tools
 - Optimised model configurations
 - Easily relocatable regional model
 - Data wrangling and post-processing tools - including output sharing
 - Training and user support
 - Idealised model versions
 - Ocean
 - Help with evaluation / tuning
 - OM3 development

- Sea ice boundary conditions.
- Two way nesting
- Coupled
 - Coupled regional models.
 - Help coordinate a community effort on spin up
 - Simpler representation of “expensive” components (e.g., aerosols) - AH: perturbed coupling
 - Methods for partial coupling
 - Link with observational community / products for evaluation

Topic 6: Paleoclimate and ice sheet modelling

Breakout aim: What are the current and future needs and where could ACCESS-NRI help support?

Summary:

- **Overall**
 - Discussing coupling ice sheet into ACCESS.
 - Projections vs paleo applications.
 - Resolution, downscaling of forcing
 - Deep time simulations with changed orography, vegetation etc
 - More user friendly ESM output, variable names
 - Tools for ancillaries, changing restarts,
- **What's the current status across the community?**
 - Ice shelf melt. Coupled ice-sheet/ocean, Ice shelf wave interaction
 - S Ocean experiments
 - Changing land sea mask, paleo experiments. Impact of changing ocean circulation on paleoclimate
 - Code management for orbital parameters
 - Paleo impact on Australia precipitation
 - Mid pliocene
 - Curation of ancillary files. Improved generation of ancillary files
 - WOMBAT, carbon isotopes
 - Ice sheet modelling with Elmer. Modelling Ice shelf ocean interaction. Ice sheet projections with Elmer Ice
 - Ice dynamics, parameterisations. Initialisation, use of obs. Ice sheet dynamics
 - Ice ocean interactions including fast ice.
 - Ice contributions to sea level rise
- **What are the current plans and ambitions?**
 - Coupling between ice sheets and ocean. BGC
 - Designing process for coupling dynamic ice sheet models to ACCESS. Stand alone model? Choice of appropriate model for present & future climate (not paleo). Upcoming workshop. (paleo needs lower resolution than acceptable for projections? Also possible differences in parameterizations). Models designed for present with more detailed physics might be ok for paleo but not vice-versa. Value of paleo for validation of projections, setting plausible ranges of parameters
 - Snapshot paleo runs rather than full transient
 - Consider asynchronous coupling of ice sheet and climate models
 - Ice sheet cavities with MOM6

- Paleo: Change masks, orography, vegetation
- New ways of running ice sheet models faster with ML
- **What is the new science we want to be able to do in the next few years?**
 - Fully interactive climate ice sheet model, Antarctica & Greenland. Antarctica more sensitive to ocean interaction.
 - North American and Eurasian ice sheets for paleo simulations.
 - Change topography, orography
 - Change vegetation. Dynamic vegetation model?
- **What can ACCESS-NRI do to support?**
 - Better use of standard names in ESM netCDF. Definitions of STASH codes.
 - Better integration of netCDF conversion to payu suite.
 - Better ways of working with restart files. Recon into the payu suite?
 - Simpler CMORization
 - Better tools/suites for ancillary files. In progress for standard present day maps. Still to consider how to do it for paleo where things are very different.
 - Future proofing: Coupling interface so that changes and upgrades to better model are simpler. Surface of ice sheet is complex, not simply via coupler? Handled by JULES at the moment?